

Supplemental Information for:

“Rate Coefficients for rotational state-to-state transitions in $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{H}_2$ collisions as predicted by Mixed Quantum/Classical Theory (MQCT)”

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Fig. S1: Dalitz plots for the comparison of 990 *state-to-state* transition rate coefficients for *o*- $\text{H}_2\text{O} + p$ - H_2 collisions at four different temperatures: 100K, 500K, 1000K, and 1500K. Each triangular plot represents a comparison between three computational methods: MQCT from this work (AT), full quantum close-coupling (CC) calculations (Daniel et al., 2011), and full quantum coupled-states (CS) calculations (Faure et al., 2023) using MOLSCAT. Different red dots within each triangle represent different transitions.

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Fig. S2: Same as in Fig. S1 but for the *effective* rate coefficients defined by Eq. (3) in the main text.

Fig. S3: Same as in Fig. S1 but for *thermal* rate coefficients defined by Eq. (4) in the main text.

Fig. S4: Comparison of 4656 *state-to-state* transition rate coefficients for quenching of 97 lower states of *o*-H₂O in collision with *p*-H₂ computed using AT-MQCT (this work) vs. those predicted by full quantum CS calculations using MOLSCAT (Faure et al., 2023) at four different temperatures: 100 K, 500 K, 1000 K, and 1500 K. Red dashed lines represent a factor of 2 difference.

Fig. S5: Same as in Fig. S4 but for the *effective* rate coefficients defined by Eq. (3) in the main text.

Fig. S6: Same as in Fig. S4 but for the *thermal* rate coefficients defined by Eq. (4) in the main text.

Fig. S7: The dependence of effective rate coefficients for o -H₂O on the initial state j_2 of p -H₂ projectile, computed by MQCT for 20 most intense transitions (identified using Fig. S4 at 1500 K) at four temperatures as indicated in the figure.

The transitions in o -H₂O are: $1_{10} \rightarrow 1_{01}$, $2_{12} \rightarrow 1_{01}$, $2_{21} \rightarrow 1_{10}$, $2_{21} \rightarrow 2_{12}$, $3_{03} \rightarrow 2_{12}$, $3_{12} \rightarrow 3_{03}$, $3_{21} \rightarrow 3_{12}$, $3_{30} \rightarrow 2_{21}$, $4_{14} \rightarrow 3_{03}$, $4_{23} \rightarrow 3_{12}$, $4_{23} \rightarrow 4_{14}$, $4_{32} \rightarrow 3_{21}$, $4_{41} \rightarrow 3_{30}$, $5_{05} \rightarrow 4_{14}$, $5_{14} \rightarrow 5_{05}$, $5_{23} \rightarrow 5_{14}$, $5_{32} \rightarrow 4_{23}$, $5_{32} \rightarrow 5_{23}$, $5_{41} \rightarrow 4_{32}$, and $5_{50} \rightarrow 4_{41}$.

Fig. S8: Same as in Fig. S7 (for the same 20 transitions in $o\text{-H}_2\text{O}$) but as a dependence on the initial state j_2 of $o\text{-H}_2$ projectile.

Fig. S9: The dependence of effective rate coefficients for $p\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ on the initial state j_2 of $p\text{-H}_2$ projectile, computed by MQCT for 20 most intense transitions identified using Fig. 5 for each individual temperature (indicated in the figure). The transitions are:

For $T = 100\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{19}$, $12_{57} \rightarrow 7_{17}$, $12_{48} \rightarrow 8_{08}$, $10_{55} \rightarrow 9_{64}$, $10_{46} \rightarrow 10_{37}$, $9_{46} \rightarrow 8_{53}$, $9_{19} \rightarrow 8_{08}$, $8_{62} \rightarrow 8_{53}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 8_{35}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 7_{35}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 6_{42}$, $8_{26} \rightarrow 6_{24}$, $8_{08} \rightarrow 7_{17}$, $8_{08} \rightarrow 5_{15}$, $7_{71} \rightarrow 6_{60}$, $7_{62} \rightarrow 6_{51}$, $7_{53} \rightarrow 6_{42}$, $7_{44} \rightarrow 6_{33}$, and $7_{17} \rightarrow 6_{06}$.

For $T = 500\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{19}$, $12_{57} \rightarrow 12_{148}$, $10_{46} \rightarrow 10_{37}$, $9_{19} \rightarrow 8_{08}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{53}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 7_{35}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 6_{42}$, $8_{26} \rightarrow 6_{24}$, $8_{08} \rightarrow 7_{17}$, $7_{71} \rightarrow 6_{60}$, $7_{62} \rightarrow 6_{51}$, $7_{53} \rightarrow 6_{42}$, $7_{44} \rightarrow 6_{33}$, $7_{26} \rightarrow 5_{24}$, $7_{17} \rightarrow 6_{06}$, $6_{60} \rightarrow 5_{51}$, $6_{51} \rightarrow 5_{42}$, $6_{06} \rightarrow 5_{15}$, and $6_{42} \rightarrow 5_{33}$.

For $T = 1000\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{19}$, $12_{57} \rightarrow 12_{148}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{53}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 7_{35}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{35} \rightarrow 6_{33}$, $8_{17} \rightarrow 7_{26}$, $8_{08} \rightarrow 7_{17}$, $7_{71} \rightarrow 6_{60}$, $7_{71} \rightarrow 5_{51}$, $7_{62} \rightarrow 6_{51}$, $7_{53} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $7_{53} \rightarrow 6_{42}$, $7_{44} \rightarrow 7_{35}$, $7_{44} \rightarrow 6_{33}$, $7_{35} \rightarrow 6_{24}$, $7_{26} \rightarrow 6_{15}$, $7_{17} \rightarrow 6_{06}$, and $6_{60} \rightarrow 5_{51}$.

For $T = 1500\text{K}$: $11_{111} \rightarrow 10_{010}$, $11_{111} \rightarrow 9_{19}$, $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{19}$, $10_{010} \rightarrow 8_{08}$, $10_{19} \rightarrow 9_{28}$, $10_{19} \rightarrow 8_{17}$, $9_{46} \rightarrow 8_{35}$, $9_{37} \rightarrow 8_{26}$, $9_{28} \rightarrow 8_{17}$, $9_{19} \rightarrow 8_{08}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{26} \rightarrow 8_{17}$, $8_{17} \rightarrow 7_{26}$, $8_{08} \rightarrow 7_{17}$, $7_{71} \rightarrow 6_{60}$, $7_{62} \rightarrow 6_{51}$, $7_{53} \rightarrow 6_{51}$, and $7_{53} \rightarrow 6_{42}$.

Fig. S10: Same as in Fig. S9, but for $p\text{-H}_2\text{O} + o\text{-H}_2$ projectile. The transitions are:

For $T = 100\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{19}$, $12_{57} \rightarrow 7_{17}$, $12_{48} \rightarrow 8_{08}$, $10_{55} \rightarrow 9_{64}$, $10_{46} \rightarrow 10_{37}$, $9_{46} \rightarrow 8_{53}$, $9_{19} \rightarrow 8_{08}$, $8_{62} \rightarrow 8_{53}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 8_{35}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 7_{35}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 6_{42}$, $8_{26} \rightarrow 6_{24}$, $8_{08} \rightarrow 7_{17}$, $8_{08} \rightarrow 5_{15}$, $7_{71} \rightarrow 6_{60}$, $7_{62} \rightarrow 6_{51}$, $7_{53} \rightarrow 6_{42}$, $7_{44} \rightarrow 6_{33}$, and $7_{17} \rightarrow 6_{06}$.

For $T = 500\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{19}$, $12_{57} \rightarrow 12_{148}$, $10_{46} \rightarrow 10_{37}$, $9_{19} \rightarrow 8_{08}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{53}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 7_{35}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 6_{42}$, $8_{26} \rightarrow 6_{24}$, $8_{08} \rightarrow 7_{17}$, $7_{71} \rightarrow 6_{60}$, $7_{62} \rightarrow 6_{51}$, $7_{53} \rightarrow 6_{42}$, $7_{44} \rightarrow 6_{33}$, $7_{26} \rightarrow 5_{24}$, $7_{17} \rightarrow 6_{06}$, $6_{60} \rightarrow 5_{51}$, $6_{51} \rightarrow 5_{42}$, $6_{06} \rightarrow 5_{15}$, and $6_{42} \rightarrow 5_{33}$.

For $T = 1000\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{19}$, $12_{57} \rightarrow 12_{148}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{53}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 7_{35}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{35} \rightarrow 6_{33}$, $8_{17} \rightarrow 7_{26}$, $8_{08} \rightarrow 7_{17}$, $7_{71} \rightarrow 6_{60}$, $7_{71} \rightarrow 5_{51}$, $7_{62} \rightarrow 6_{51}$, $7_{53} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $7_{53} \rightarrow 6_{42}$, $7_{44} \rightarrow 7_{35}$, $7_{44} \rightarrow 6_{33}$, $7_{35} \rightarrow 6_{24}$, $7_{26} \rightarrow 6_{15}$, $7_{17} \rightarrow 6_{06}$, and $6_{60} \rightarrow 5_{51}$.

For $T = 1500\text{K}$: $11_{111} \rightarrow 10_{010}$, $11_{111} \rightarrow 9_{19}$, $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{19}$, $10_{010} \rightarrow 8_{08}$, $10_{19} \rightarrow 9_{28}$, $10_{19} \rightarrow 8_{17}$, $9_{46} \rightarrow 8_{35}$, $9_{37} \rightarrow 8_{26}$, $9_{28} \rightarrow 8_{17}$, $9_{19} \rightarrow 8_{08}$, $8_{53} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{44} \rightarrow 7_{44}$, $8_{26} \rightarrow 8_{17}$, $8_{17} \rightarrow 7_{26}$, $8_{08} \rightarrow 7_{17}$, $7_{71} \rightarrow 6_{60}$, $7_{62} \rightarrow 6_{51}$, $7_{53} \rightarrow 6_{51}$, and $7_{53} \rightarrow 6_{42}$.

Fig. S11: The dependence of effective rate coefficients for *o*-H₂O on the initial state j_2 of *p*-H₂ projectile, computed by MQCT for 20 most intense transitions for each individual temperature (indicated in the figure). The transitions are:

For $T = 100\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{09}$, $10_{110} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $13_{49} \rightarrow 13_{310}$, $11_{83} \rightarrow 10_{92}$, $10_{74} \rightarrow 9_{81}$, $9_{54} \rightarrow 8_{45}$, $9_{45} \rightarrow 9_{36}$, $9_{09} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $8_{54} \rightarrow 7_{43}$, $8_{18} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $8_{18} \rightarrow 5_{05}$, $7_{70} \rightarrow 6_{61}$, $7_{61} \rightarrow 6_{52}$, $7_{52} \rightarrow 7_{43}$, $7_{52} \rightarrow 6_{43}$, $7_{43} \rightarrow 7_{34}$, $7_{16} \rightarrow 6_{25}$, $7_{07} \rightarrow 6_{16}$, $6_{61} \rightarrow 5_{50}$, and $6_{52} \rightarrow 6_{43}$.

For $T = 500\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{09}$, $10_{110} \rightarrow 8_{18}$, $12_{67} \rightarrow 12_{58}$, $11_{47} \rightarrow 11_{38}$, $10_{38} \rightarrow 10_{29}$, $9_{72} \rightarrow 9_{63}$, $9_{63} \rightarrow 9_{54}$, $9_{54} \rightarrow 9_{45}$, $9_{27} \rightarrow 7_{25}$, $9_{09} \rightarrow 8_{18}$, $8_{72} \rightarrow 8_{63}$, $8_{54} \rightarrow 7_{43}$, $8_{18} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $7_{70} \rightarrow 6_{61}$, $7_{61} \rightarrow 6_{52}$, $7_{52} \rightarrow 6_{43}$, $7_{07} \rightarrow 6_{16}$, $6_{61} \rightarrow 5_{50}$, $6_{52} \rightarrow 5_{41}$, and $6_{16} \rightarrow 5_{05}$.

For $T = 1000\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{09}$, $10_{110} \rightarrow 8_{18}$, $12_{67} \rightarrow 12_{58}$, $11_{65} \rightarrow 10_{74}$, $11_{47} \rightarrow 11_{38}$, $10_{38} \rightarrow 10_{29}$, $9_{72} \rightarrow 7_{25}$, $9_{09} \rightarrow 8_{18}$, $8_{81} \rightarrow 8_{72}$, $8_{72} \rightarrow 8_{63}$, $8_{63} \rightarrow 8_{54}$, $8_{18} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $7_{70} \rightarrow 6_{61}$, $7_{61} \rightarrow 6_{52}$, $7_{52} \rightarrow 6_{43}$, $7_{34} \rightarrow 7_{25}$, $7_{07} \rightarrow 6_{16}$, $6_{61} \rightarrow 5_{50}$, $6_{52} \rightarrow 5_{41}$, and $6_{16} \rightarrow 5_{05}$.

For $T = 1500\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{09}$, $10_{110} \rightarrow 9_{09}$, $12_{85} \rightarrow 11_{92}$, $11_{74} \rightarrow 11_{65}$, $11_{65} \rightarrow 11_{56}$, $11_{56} \rightarrow 11_{47}$, $10_{47} \rightarrow 10_{38}$, $9_{72} \rightarrow 9_{63}$, $9_{63} \rightarrow 9_{54}$, $9_{54} \rightarrow 9_{45}$, $9_{54} \rightarrow 8_{63}$, $9_{45} \rightarrow 9_{36}$, $9_{09} \rightarrow 8_{18}$, $8_{81} \rightarrow 8_{72}$, $8_{72} \rightarrow 8_{63}$, $8_{63} \rightarrow 8_{54}$, $8_{18} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $7_{70} \rightarrow 6_{61}$, $7_{61} \rightarrow 6_{52}$, and $7_{07} \rightarrow 6_{16}$.

Fig. S12: Same as in Fig. S11, but for $o\text{-H}_2\text{O} + o\text{-H}_2$ projectile. The transitions are:

For $T = 100\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{09}$, $10_{110} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $13_{49} \rightarrow 13_{310}$, $11_{83} \rightarrow 10_{92}$, $10_{74} \rightarrow 9_{81}$, $9_{54} \rightarrow 8_{45}$, $9_{45} \rightarrow 9_{36}$, $9_{09} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $8_{54} \rightarrow 7_{43}$, $8_{18} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $8_{18} \rightarrow 5_{05}$, $7_{70} \rightarrow 6_{61}$, $7_{61} \rightarrow 6_{52}$, $7_{52} \rightarrow 7_{43}$, $7_{52} \rightarrow 6_{43}$, $7_{43} \rightarrow 7_{34}$, $7_{16} \rightarrow 6_{25}$, $7_{07} \rightarrow 6_{16}$, $6_{61} \rightarrow 5_{50}$, and $6_{52} \rightarrow 6_{43}$.

For $T = 500\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{09}$, $10_{110} \rightarrow 8_{18}$, $12_{67} \rightarrow 12_{58}$, $11_{47} \rightarrow 11_{38}$, $10_{38} \rightarrow 10_{29}$, $9_{72} \rightarrow 9_{63}$, $9_{63} \rightarrow 9_{54}$, $9_{54} \rightarrow 9_{45}$, $9_{27} \rightarrow 7_{25}$, $9_{09} \rightarrow 8_{18}$, $8_{72} \rightarrow 8_{63}$, $8_{54} \rightarrow 7_{43}$, $8_{18} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $7_{70} \rightarrow 6_{61}$, $7_{61} \rightarrow 6_{52}$, $7_{52} \rightarrow 6_{43}$, $7_{07} \rightarrow 6_{16}$, $6_{61} \rightarrow 5_{50}$, $6_{52} \rightarrow 5_{41}$, and $6_{16} \rightarrow 5_{05}$.

For $T = 1000\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{09}$, $10_{110} \rightarrow 8_{18}$, $12_{67} \rightarrow 12_{58}$, $11_{65} \rightarrow 10_{74}$, $11_{47} \rightarrow 11_{38}$, $10_{38} \rightarrow 10_{29}$, $9_{72} \rightarrow 7_{25}$, $9_{09} \rightarrow 8_{18}$, $8_{81} \rightarrow 8_{72}$, $8_{72} \rightarrow 8_{63}$, $8_{63} \rightarrow 8_{54}$, $8_{18} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $7_{70} \rightarrow 6_{61}$, $7_{61} \rightarrow 6_{52}$, $7_{52} \rightarrow 6_{43}$, $7_{34} \rightarrow 7_{25}$, $7_{07} \rightarrow 6_{16}$, $6_{61} \rightarrow 5_{50}$, $6_{52} \rightarrow 5_{41}$, and $6_{16} \rightarrow 5_{05}$.

For $T = 1500\text{K}$: $10_{010} \rightarrow 9_{09}$, $10_{110} \rightarrow 9_{09}$, $12_{85} \rightarrow 11_{92}$, $11_{74} \rightarrow 11_{65}$, $11_{65} \rightarrow 11_{56}$, $11_{56} \rightarrow 11_{47}$, $10_{47} \rightarrow 10_{38}$, $9_{72} \rightarrow 9_{63}$, $9_{63} \rightarrow 9_{54}$, $9_{54} \rightarrow 9_{45}$, $9_{54} \rightarrow 8_{63}$, $9_{45} \rightarrow 9_{36}$, $9_{09} \rightarrow 8_{18}$, $8_{81} \rightarrow 8_{72}$, $8_{72} \rightarrow 8_{63}$, $8_{63} \rightarrow 8_{54}$, $8_{18} \rightarrow 7_{07}$, $7_{70} \rightarrow 6_{61}$, $7_{61} \rightarrow 6_{52}$, and $7_{07} \rightarrow 6_{16}$.